

A CONCEPTUAL STUDY ON STUDENTS PERCEPTION AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS MOOCS

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ABSTRACT

The rapid development and innovation in technologies have strongly affected all parts of our day-to-day life activities & even the education sector has not been left behind changes in technology and has also caused a change in learning style pattern.

The purpose of this conceptual paper is to provide information about students' perception and attitude towards MOOCs and to identify the causes which affect enrolment in MOOCs by students. The review of the literature paper analyses describes, evaluates and summaries previous studies carried out in the concerned field.

The findings indicate that students have a typically positive attitude toward their courses. Personal relevance, educational value, and life skills are three variables that influence students' perceptions towards MOOC courses and there are six themes that revolve around students' attitudes: - Reliability, accessibility, content, learning, communication, and outcomes.

Keywords: - Perception, Attitude, Students, MOOCs, Online Learning, Pandemic.

INTRODUCTION

In the current environment, traditional teaching i.e., physical classroom learning is losing its dominance as the only option for learning (Nguyen, 2015). The Online courses were established in the early '90s & in 21st-century MOOCs (Massive Open Online Courses) rules learning through the internet. MOOCs were established in 2008,

MOOCs were only famous in foreign countries like USA, UK & Arab Countries, etc. But now the Indian government has also taken initiatives for development in Indian education. Some of the current studies found that India (16.97%) holds the second position after the US (27.15%) in terms of MOOCs enrollment (Chatterjee & Nath, 2015).

The Global Pandemic Covid-19 came as a boon to the digital world many people were able to access online educational platforms or MOOCs for their skill development, experience, etc.\

EVOLUTION OF MOOCS

MEANING OF MOOCS

According to MOOC.org Massive, Open Online Courses (MOOCs) are free & open online courses accessible for anyone to register.

MOOCs are open video-based educational content, lectures, study guides, and forums that are made available to a large number of people who want to attend a course or learn something new via an internet platform. Because of its time and location flexibility, MOOCs bring together researchers like-minded other students from all over the globe. (Baturay, 2015).

(Pampouri et al., 2021) Concluded that MOOCs are a bold educational innovation that is perfectly aligned with technological, economic, and social advancements. They make use of modern technology to provide a diverse range of education aimed at a diverse audience and cover a wide range of themes. They use a range of teaching approaches in order to satisfy each learner's unique demands. Despite the fact that the first MOOCs were launched only a few years ago, we are witnessing their rapid expansion and diffusion. In summary, MOOCs encourage participation in lifelong cooperative learning approaches, offer open, accessible, elevated, and free education, and are available for personal improvement or to meet specific employment criteria. The following phrase vividly describes the whole philosophy of MOOCs: "MOOCs allow teachers to teach more students in one subject than they would in a lifetime(Aparicio et al., 2019).

MOOCs issues an affordable & dynamic way to learn and adopt the new skills, advance your career, and bring standard educational experiences at scale. Millions of people across the world use Massive open online courses to learn for various reasons, like career development, experience, new skills, lifelong learning, job requirement, and more...

In India, MOOCs are altering the way students learn and supporting them in reskilling and upskilling, and they are paving the way for the next wave of education and learning. The Indian government has created the Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds (SWAYAM) and the National Programme on Technology Enhanced Learning (NPTEL) MOOC platforms in collaboration with Indian colleges that offer online and paid courses. Private firms in this industry include Udacity, Open2Study, MooKIT, IITBX, Coursera, edX, and Udemy. (Pillai and Sivathanu 2020).

MOOC has become a catch-all term for a number of projects. 'cMOOCs,' or connectivist MOOCs,' emphasize the development of digital artifacts as an intrinsic part of the learning process and focus on knowledge generation within a network of learners in terms of philosophy. 'xMOOCs,' on the other hand, are geared toward knowledge dissemination and include pedagogic, specialist training (commonly via lecture videos). The number of students in a course might range from just a few dozens to hundreds of thousands. Despite their name, not all MOOCs are open, and the vast majority of them do not offer free content for unrestricted access and use outside of the learning activities. (Welsh & Dragusin, 2013). In terms of accreditation, several offer course certificates as proof of completion, with only a small percentage granting transferable university credits thus far. The majority of courses that offer recognised accreditation enable the students to pay for and complete a final assessment or project. Coursera has dropped its strategy of providing a free 'lower category' Declaration of Accomplishment in favour of charging for all certificates. In terms of functioning, many MOOCs are completely online courses designed for personal development and curiosity. Those given for credit offer an alternative way of learning to existing face-to-face courses, allowing more people to enrol in higher-level courses. A rising variety of blended learning or flipped-classroom models exist, in which the MOOC is not an externally available course but rather an integral part of a face-to-face programme(Sandeen, 2013)

THE FOLLOWING ARE THE KEY CHARACTERISTICS OF A MOOC

- a) Freedom of choice: MOOCs give students the freedom to select where, when, how, with whom, and even what they want to learn.
- b) Diverse learners: MOOCs attract students from many walks of life of the universe and encourage other ways of thinking and reading.
- b) Connectivity: MOOCs keep individuals connected all the time interacting with one another and attempting to build knowledge.
- d) Self-paced: MOOCs give learners the freedom to choose when and how they want to learn. MOOCs feature papers that students can use to learn how and when they choose.
- c) Lifetime Learning: Learners improve their ability to learn throughout their lives, participation in a MOOC.
- f) Certificates and Recognitions: Most MOOCs award certificates and recognitions.

A kind of appreciation for successfully completing a course, based on the results of a final computer-assisted evaluation.

FIGURE 1.1 WORLD-WIDE GROWTH OF MOOCS (EXCLUDE CHINA)

SOURCE: - <https://www.classcentral.com/report/mooc-stats-2020/>

Explanation: - Figure 1.1 depicts the growth of enrolment in MOOCs from the year 2012 to the year 2021. The chart shows the overall growth of MOOCs across global except China. In total, we can see the drastic change in enrolment in MOOCs from the year 2019 due to the Global pandemic Covid-19. As a result, of pandemics and lockdown people started working from home and many working professionals were laid off and got enough time and opportunity to further their studies.

Figure 1.2 Web Traffic During the Pandemic

SOURCE: - <https://www.classcentral.com/report/mooc-stats-pandemic/>

Explanation: - Figure 1.2 shows the web traffic during the global pandemic Covid-19 on national and international MOOCs platforms. As we can see that the highest traffic of learners is on Coursera and the 2nd highest on the edx. There are various reasons for the enrolment in courses provided by coursera because it provides access to a large number of courses from different universities on a single platform.

OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH

1. To study the perception and attitude of Students toward MOOCs.
2. To identify factors affecting students' perception in MOOCs enrolment.
3. To identify factors affecting students' attitude in MOOCs enrolment
4. To find out constraints involved in completion of MOOCs.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The current study is descriptive & conclusive in nature. The study is based on the secondary sources collected from various research papers, review papers, articles, and e-sources.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Under this section reviewed conclusion of several research papers and articles was done by the researcher to draw more clarity about the meaning of MOOCs and factors affecting students' perception and attitude towards MOOCs.

According to this research, MOOCs are open, participatory, and distributed in nature (Baturay, 2015). (Ali et al., 2010) According to their research, students in online courses were expected to be self-responsible, self-motivated, and able to communicate with teachers. Personal qualities, as well as one's cultural background, have an impact on one's ability to succeed in online courses.

(Salunke et al., 2021) in their study concluded that online courses provide flexibility by this feature is becoming more popular. In the future reliability of physical institutes may be reduced because of online courses. Under online courses, only theoretical knowledge can be imparted and will also decrease the interaction among students which can lead to social isolation as well. MOOCs were rapidly emerging method of education by which anyone can learn from anywhere. MOOCs appears to be on the 4th stage in an evolving process in online education (Masters, 2012)

According to the findings of the survey, students who had a positive learning experience claimed that they would suggest MOOCs to their friends 90% of the time, and 88 percent of learners said that the MOOCs they studied had a positive impact on them (Abeer & Miri, 2014).

The findings demonstrate that MOOCs can be a valuable digital career development platform for professionals seeking to gain new skills and information, particularly when such opportunities and resources are free and not readily available in their immediate area.

Students should think about the versatility of the course schedule, the instructor's reputation, and the quality of the materials. (Liu et al., 2015) Adult learners will find MOOCs to be a helpful learning platform because of its user-friendliness, accessibility, and sharing opportunities. Because adult learners have various duties, such features in their learning platform were considered as helpful in optimising their learning potential (Abd Majid et al., 2019).

(Rai & Chunrao, 2016) It was found that most of the factors that determine success or failure are solely personal, as most students are sincerely interested in completing their courses, and most of these students are enthralled by the status of universities, the quality of their courses, and the enjoyment they derive from completing difficult assignments. Other issues such as bad Internet access, a lack of understanding of MOOCs, language barriers, and learning potential are not addressed in this research.

(Gamage et al., 2016) This paper claims that MOOCs are a type of eLearning technology that is gaining popularity around the world owing to its unique characteristics of being free, huge, and available to everyone with an internet connection. On the other side, as the number of MOOCs providers and courses grows, quality issues arise, and many MOOCs suppliers fail to achieve the goals of their consumers.

Despite the increased benefits and efficiency, the number of persons taking MOOCs from developing countries (particularly India) is small. India, as a promising educational hub, provides a promising environment for the large-scale adoption of MOOCs. However, various issues and obstacles, such as low online learning and a lack of a robust digital infrastructure, obstruct the widespread adoption of MOOCs. Despite all of the obstacles, India leads the developing world in terms of MOOC enrollment. The writers have explored certain significant concerns with MOOCs, particularly in the Higher Education system, as well as popularizing them widely in order to fully exploit India's potential education market. The authors have also experimented with several number of different approaches to substantial implementation in a virtual learning environment (Chatterjee & Nath, 2015)

Huge numbers of people from all over the world have enrolled in MOOCs; nevertheless, a detailed examination of the student demographics reveals that the vast majority of those represented by these courses have previously completed university education. As a result, they appear to be increasing rather than expanding access to higher education at the moment. Some possible explanations for these findings include: people with a higher education possess better "access" to MOOCs; they are prepared for the self-learning required in these courses, and they are less concerned about recognition than learners without a higher education who must "prove" their skills to employers. MOOCs appear to be meeting the needs of "knowledge workers" in terms of updating their skills and continuing professional development, despite changes in higher education funding and austerity measures. As a result, MOOCs appear to be better supporting the field of continuous professional development at the moment. MOOCs can also be beneficial to casual learners (Liyanagunawardena, 2015).

(Funieru & Lazaroiu, 2016) This study adds to our knowledge of the characteristics of the most widely utilised MOOC providers, which can be used as a model for future platforms. Understanding these elements, particularly what makes the platforms stand out, whether it's novel ideas or sophisticated technologies, is crucial for both users and developers who want to help students reach their learning goals. As MOOCs gain in popularity, more research should be conducted in order to suggest new features that will boost student engagement and draw attention to this freely available style of learning.

(Saadatmand & Kumpulainen, 2014) The writers of this research explored learning experiences and activities in cMOOCs. The findings demonstrate that MOOC participation necessitates the development of self-organization, self-motivation, and a decent level of technological skill in order to manage the number of materials and a more open style. cMOOC participants employ a variety of technologies and networking skills. The nature of cMOOCs necessitates students taking active roles in shaping activities and collaborating to achieve goals in an open and honest manner. Learners choose which tools and resources to use, which texts to master, and which connections to rely on in cMOOCs because they are self-organized. Students select the tools and resources that best suit their learning objectives and interests.

(Sukhbaatar et al., 2018) The major goal of this research was to look at Mongolian students' perceptions of MOOCs and the impact of accessibility, competencies, and interests on their e-learning experience. According to the findings, instructors should focus more on disseminating information about the benefits of educational technologies, as well as course facilitation and efficient delivery. Because students are eager to participate despite a lack of access or abilities, it is critical to provide them with a positive initial experience in order for them to engage more fully. Education professors have a good attitude toward MOOCs because they believe that by participating in them, they would be able to keep their knowledge up to date and learn new teaching methods, which will improve their teaching quality and, in turn, their students' academic success. In addition, the findings of this study demonstrated that education lecturers have a favourable view about MOOCs. The engaging, pleasant, and cooperating aspects of MOOC platforms, which they believe would be fascinating in obtaining and updating their knowledge and skills, contributed to education lecturers' favourable attitude toward MOOCs. The findings of this study also demonstrated that there is a considerable difference in perception between male and female education professors on Massive Open Online Courses, with female lecturers having a significant advantage. Furthermore, data demonstrated a large gender gap in the attitudes of male and female education instructors, with men lecturers favouring female lecturers (Caleb et al., 2020).

- Under this section reviewed conclusion of several research papers and articles was done by the researcher to draw more clarity about the constraints involved in completion of MOOCs.
- Dropout rates are unquestionably high, but there are also worries that completing a MOOC appears to be more doable for some groups of individuals. Some observers have

emphasised MOOCs' disorderly and transformatory potential (Conole, 2016), and it has been suggested that MOOCs are well-suited to students who face impediments to education, such as geography, individual circumstances, or a lack of opportunity (Escher et al., 2014). Others refer to MOOC students whose lives have been changed as a result of their participation in the course (Devlin, 2013). However, preliminary research suggests that technology, language, learning skills, and digital skills all pose challenges in practise (Sinclair & Kalvala, 2016).

(Sinclair & Kalvala, 2016) Concluded that Students drop out of MOOCs for a variety of reasons. High attrition rates are likely to be a symptom of difficulties within the course, at least in part. However, owing to the wide range of causes, they aren't a reliable indicator of what's happening in a MOOC. We need to think about the content of the courses and the things they include in more depth. Dropout and completion rate studies are widespread and practical among all of the themes. They are predicated on the reality that, while the number of people who enroll in a MOOC course is large at beginning, the number of people who finish all of the course work is small. For various reasons, some students are inattentive and perhaps even drop out of the course midway through. Experts and researchers feel that the completion rate is linked to both the MOOCs features and the demands of the learners (LIU & LI, 2017).

Since the number of student comments has a strong positive effect on the number of MOOC completion, which represents the expansion of eWOM, this is suggested that the MOOCs platform inspires students to enroll in the MOOCs learning forum, for example, by allowing learners to specify friends when posting. On the one hand, it can enhance social learning in MOOCs, and on the other, it can assist MOOCs learners in receiving timely attention and responses from others, thereby encouraging MOOCs learners to talk and interact in the MOOCs learning forum. As a result, MOOC learners' motivation to complete the course can be increased (Wu & Li, 2020). According to (Knöös & Rääf ,2021) too demanding, too much effort, lack of time, not improving CV, not an engaging course, lack of self-discipline, not a prerequisite, not good delivery, and inadequate quality of video material are nine demotivating factors which contribute to a learner not finishing a course. These elements, according to the participants, contributed to the students' failure to complete a course. (Moore & Wang ,2021) looked at the effect of motivational attitudes in completing an open online course, and found that students' performance was substantially correlated with their educational background, gender, and motivation. Females outperformed males, while pupils with intrinsically motivating attitudes outperformed those with extrinsically motivating attitudes. The course material, delivery time, and a student's attendance to course activities, as well as the length of the course, all played a role in the MOOC dropout trend, according to (Rawat et al., 2021).

(Aldowah et al.,2020) used a multiple-criteria decision-making method to identify the essential aspects and potential causal ties accountable for the high dropout rate in MOOCs. They discovered twelve indicators linked to students dropping out of online courses, separated into four components. Six key criteria that positively influences student dropout in MOOCs were identified: academic skills and talents, prior experience, course design,

assessment, social engagement, and social protection. Other factors that were identified to have a modest impact on student dropout in the study included communication, program complexity and duration, commitment, enthusiasm, and family/work conditions. Dropouts from mocs should then be judged against learners' personal goals rather than completing all of the course's necessary activities and receiving the certificate, according to some experts(Henderikx et al., 2017), (Stracke, 2017). Learners are considered successful if they complete the MOOC as planned or more, and dropouts if they complete the MOOC less than planned or exit during the course's duration (Henderikx et al., 2017). This is because learners' personal goals may differ from those of the course organizers(Henderikx et al., 2017), (Stracke, 2017) . For example, students may merely wish to engage oneself with the course without planning to complete it (de Freitas et al., 2015), or they may solely want to use course resources afterwards and not in reference to the MOOC (Stracke, 2017).

Illness ,a terrible experience with the material, the online style of the course, family obligations, and employment circumstances can all have an adverse effect on course completion(Shapiro et al., 2017). As they attend the course, dropouts have more problems at home and at work (Rõõm et al., 2020). Working has also enhanced the likelihood of completing the course (GOMEZ-ZERMENO & ALEMAN DE LA GARZA, 2016), since learners use their working time to perform course activities (Rõõm et al., 2020). Lower education levels reduce the likelihood of completion in the MOOC based on learner characteristics (GOMEZ-ZERMENO & ALEMAN DE LA GARZA, 2016), (Shapiro et al., 2017). Course completion is influenced by learners' consciousness, effectiveness and enthusiasm (Eriksson et al., 2016). Not all motivation-related criteria change between dropouts and completers, according to research (Luik et al., 2018).

- The researcher found out some variables or factors that affect enrolment in MOOCs

Source: - Self Made

Reputation: A goods and service reputation develops through time and is usually based on personal experience with the service , word-of-mouth recommendations, and marketing activities aimed at establishing a status or shared perception of the product or service . Furthermore, a consumer's view of a platform reputation is influenced not just by the product's and service brand identification , but also by the entire logistics chain. Even if a consumer trusts a product's and service producer, he or she may change their minds about the product and service after seeing it in a market that he identifies with low-cost, substandard goods and services.

1. **The credibility of the courses:** Credibility is the quality that makes a platform to be trusted and believed in. Credible courses are those which are recognized or accredited.
2. **Fees:** The fees involved for getting enrolled also determine a student's will to opt for the course. Often the platforms offer both paid and free courses, also some courses offer the content for free but to get a certificate, a fee has to be paid.
3. **Time Duration:** The time involved determines the student preference for the course. On average, online courses have a time -span of about 8 to 9 weeks. Also, the courses can either be self-paced or instructor-paced which affects the learner's choice.
4. **Certification:** The certificates also play an important role, as these are the proof that the learner has completed and mastered the skills and also add up to achievements. When organizations recruit new employees or evaluate their performance, Certified Professionals are given preference. A certification course allows an individual to demonstrate his competency, dedication to the field, and experience in his specialized subject area while also assisting with employment growth. It is a credential gained by a person who certifies to a corporation that he is capable of executing a job.
5. **Accessibility and Flexibility:** - E-learning, in order to be truly effective, must be as adaptable and accessible as the claims made about it. Those who are unable to attend university during regular lecture hours frequently use online courses. This necessitates the availability of e-learning platforms, including feedback services, 24 hours a day. This isn't simply vital for individuals who work full-time; on-demand is ingrained in students' lives (for example, with television), and they have come to expect it from their education. Feedback must also be provided quickly. Because online students do not have the same flexibility in their daily schedules, they may only have time to complete assignments at the last minute, necessitating timely and effective grading of draughts.

FACTORS AFFECTING PERCEPTION

According to S. P. Robbins, perception can be defined as "the process by which individuals organize and interpret their sensory impressions to give meaning to their environments."

Factors Affecting Perception: - (Solomon, 2006).

1. **Need and Desires:** - Need and desires of a person plays a vital role in perception. A person gets to know exactly what he/she wants from the products or services from their need and desires. Generally, needs and desires were created by advertisements of products and services.
2. **Own Experience:** - A customer's perception is heavily influenced by his or her personal experience while purchasing and subsequently utilising a product. If the customer has a positive experience with the goods and services, he or she will purchase the product or use the services again.
3. **Advertising:** - Advertisement helps to build a positive perception. We can say that the advertisement is the biggest influencing factor of perception because the customer gets knowledge about the product and services mainly through advertisement. When consumers see a product and service advertised someplace,

they are more inspired to buy it; they also feel safer buying a product and service they have seen advertised. A consumer's level of credibility for a brand they've seen advertised grows with time. They were also seen gathering product information from advertisements, learning about the product's usage and benefits, and then making a purchase choice based on that information.

4. **Influencers:** - Influencers who promote products and businesses have grown commonplace in the lives of customers. Several times a day, especially on social media, we can uncover an influencer advertising campaign. Influencers advocate a wide range of things, including clothing, shoes, and cosmetics, as well as services. Most individuals will buy a product after seeing it used and tested by someone else. It's fantastic when a referral comes from someone we can trust.
5. **Customer Reviews:** - Individuals can now share their product assessments, thoughts, and recommendations thanks to the increasing rise of internet communities. This is likely one of the most important internet product information sources that has a significant impact on consumer buying intentions. Despite the fact that the literature on the impact of Online Consumer reviews on consumer behaviour is divided, it is obvious that OCRs have a substantial impact on customer decision-making. The majority of individuals read customer reviews before purchasing a product, implying that customer reviews have a significant impact on perception. The number of stars awarded by customers is used to assess the quality of items and services.
6. **Use of social media:** - Consequently, social media is the most powerful tool for changing or influencing customer impression. A corporation can create a positive perception in the minds of customers by sharing photographs, videos, and other content relevant to goods and services on the internet.

- **Factors affecting Attitude:** -

Consumer attitude can be defined as a feeling of favorable or unfavorable evaluation of an object. Attitude plays an important role in liking and disliking, accepting and rejecting the products or services (Solomon, 2006). Consumer attitude essentially includes beliefs, feelings, and behavioural intentions towards some object.

Factors influencing Attitude: -(Solomon, 2006).

1. **Social Influences:** - In any culture, there is a majority of people who desire to live in peace. They make an effort to avoid unnecessary disagreement with others. They are naturally prone to create positive views regarding the majority of individuals and issues. Our attitudes can help us build and sustain strong relationships with members of groups that we value. Social roles and standards can have a big impact on people's opinions. The way people are supposed to behave in a specific role or setting is referred to as their social role. Society's regulations regarding what acts are acceptable are referred to as social norms.
2. **Direct Instructions:** - Direct instruction can have a significant impact on attitude formation. For example, someone may provide information regarding the value of a

specific online course in terms of obtaining a higher-paying job. As a result, a person's opinion toward that online course can be favourable or bad depending on their expertise.

3. **Family:-** Members of one's family play a vital part in the shaping of one's attitudes. The influence of family on one's attitude is very profound and difficult to modify.
4. **Bias:** - Bias is defined as a set of fixed thoughts or judgments that one develops through time. An attitude can include bias, in which we make judgments an issue without giving all the evidence a fair hearing. Biasness is preconceived notions or judgments that lead to attitudes toward other people, objects, or situations. We may perceive a person accused of a crime as guilty regardless of the evidence if we are prejudiced against him. We can also be biased in one direction or the other.
5. **Own Experience:** - Personal experiences have left a deep imprint in order to serve as the foundation for attitudes. As a result, when personal experience contains emotional aspects, the attitude will be easier to create. Appreciation will be a more in-depth experience and a longer trail in situations involving emotions.
6. **Media:** -. The mass media, such as television and radio, have a significant impact on molding people's attitudes and beliefs as a means of communication. There is new information about something that lays the groundwork for the development of new cognitive views about it. If strong enough, suggestive messages that include information can provide basic emotions in evaluating something and creating attitudes toward it.
7. **Educational Institutions:** - Because they create the foundation of thinking and moral notions within the individual, educational and religious institutions have a great influence in forming attitudes as a system. Understanding the good and bad, the dividing line between what can be done and what cannot be done, comes from the heart of educational and religious activities and teachings.
8. **Economic Status and Occupation:** - Our economic and occupational status also have a role in shaping our attitudes. They influence our attitudes toward labour unions and management, as well as our perceptions of whether specific laws are 'good' or 'bad.' Our current and future opinions are influenced by our socioeconomic background. Other aspects, such as relevance, reliability, availability, and associated information, are reflected in attitudes in addition to favourable or negative judgments. In the study of social psychology, attitudes are essential because they impact how much attention and judgement an individual gives to a particular subject.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSION

This paper consolidates the evidence related to MOOCs enrolment and factors affecting student's perception and attitude. On the whole review of papers, it was found that most of the factors that determine success or failure are solely personal, as most students are genuinely interested in completing their courses, and most of these students are captivated more by the prestige of universities, the quality of their courses, and the enjoyment they derive from completing difficult assignments. Other factors such as bad Broadband internet, a

lack of understanding of MOOCs, language barriers, and learning potential are not addressed in this research.

Our findings show that the majority of students see such MOOCs as an effective environment for their professional growth, and they are keen to incorporate collaborative writing models into their language course design and classroom practice.

When MOOCs are used in the learning process, female students are more deep learners and feel less threatened than male students, according to a study.

The findings reveal that learners who enjoy learning and comprehending new concepts are strongly committed to MOOCs, whereas learners who prefer to learn independently are less committed.

According to the conclusions of the research article, four aspects have a substantial impact on a student's perception: E-learner, competency, external influence, system interaction, and social influence.

The findings indicate that students have a typically positive attitude toward their courses. Personal relevance, educational value, and life skills are three variables that influence students' perceptions towards MOOC courses and six themes revolve around students' attitudes: - Reliability, accessibility, content, learning, communication, and outcomes.

It was also found that there were nine demotivating causes contribute to a learner not complete a course: too difficult, too much effort, lack of time, not improving CV, not an engaging course, lack of self-discipline, not a prerequisite, poor delivery, and inadequate video content quality. According to the participants, these factors led to the students' inability to complete a course.

This is basically a review study so that we may undertake a research study to better understand the aspects that influence students' perceptions and attitudes towards MOOCs.

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